
Spontaneous Pregnancy and Biochemical Improvement in a Woman with Non-Classical Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia Treated with Modified-Release Hydrocortisone

A Case Report

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Abstract

Introduction. Non-classical congenital adrenal hyperplasia (NCCAH) due to 21-hydroxylase deficiency is associated with chronic hyperandrogenism, menstrual irregularities, and subfertility. Modified-release hydrocortisone (MRHC) therapy, which mimics physiological cortisol rhythms, may enhance reproductive outcomes. Clinical experience with MRHC in the preconception setting is still limited.

Case presentation. A 33-year-old woman with genetically confirmed NCCAH (homozygous c.841G>T; p.Val281Leu in CYP21A2) and a history of long-standing oligomenorrhea achieved spontaneous pregnancy after four months of MRHC therapy (5 mg AM + 10 mg PM), following long-term treatment with immediate-release hydrocortisone (IRHC). The hormonal profile showed a significant decrease in adrenal androgens under MRHC (17-hydroxyprogesterone from 56 to 28.6 ng/mL; androstenedione from 6 to 5.31 ng/mL; testosterone from 0.72 to 0.63 ng/mL). After conception, MRHC was discontinued and IRHC reintroduced. Pregnancy was uneventful, and a healthy male neonate was delivered vaginally at term.

Conclusion. MRHC may offer clinical and biochemical benefits in women with NCCAH seeking pregnancy, with favorable modulation of the androgenic profile. This case supports MRHC as a valuable preconception therapeutic strategy. However, IRHC remains the standard during gestation. Further prospective data are needed to guide long-term endocrine and reproductive care in this population.

Keywords: *Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH); Non-Classical Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia (NCCAH); modified-release hydrocortisone (MRHC); instant-release hydrocortisone (IRHC); 17-hydroxyprogesterone (17OHP); fertility; pregnancy; endocrinology.*

Introduction

Non-classical congenital adrenal hyperplasia (NCCAH) is an autosomal recessive disorder most commonly caused by partial 21-hydroxylase deficiency due to mutations in the *CYP21A2* gene. The p.Val281Leu missense variant is frequently associated with this non-classical phenotype, characterized by preserved cortisol synthesis and excessive adrenal androgen production. Clinical manifestations may include precocious pubarche, acne, hirsutism, oligomenorrhea, and subfertility [1].

Standard treatment with glucocorticoids (GCs), mostly immediate-release hydrocortisone (IRHC), aims to suppress corticotropin (ACTH) and reduce androgen production. However, IRHC's short half-life often results in non-physiological peaks and troughs [2]. Modified-release hydrocortisone (MRHC), by contrast, is formulated to mimic the circadian cortisol rhythm via a dual-release mechanism, with ~20% released immediately and the remaining 80% released over 6–10 hours [3]. Taken in the evening, MRHC reaches peak cortisol levels in the early morning, suppressing the nocturnal ACTH surge and improving hormonal control [4].

Here, we describe the case of a woman with NCCAH and long-standing IRHC therapy who conceived spontaneously after switching to MRHC (*brand name: Efmody*[®]). This case highlights both clinical and biochemical improvement, underscoring MRHC's potential as a pre-conceptional treatment in NCCAH.

Methods

A 33-year-old woman with NCCAH, diagnosed at age seven due to signs of precocious puberty, was referred for preconception assessment. Genetic testing confirmed homozygosity for *CYP21A2* variant c.841G>T (p.Val281Leu), consistent with a non-classical phenotype. She had regular follow-up since diagnosis and was treated continuously with IRHC.

She had a history of dyslipidemia and used etonogestrel 0.120 mg/day + ethinylestradiol 0.015 mg/day (*brand name: NuvaRing*[®]) for contraception for several years, discontinued in 2021. She experienced 6 months of amenorrhea followed by persistent oligomenorrhea. No recent gynecological evaluation had been performed before presentation. Nulligravida, non-smoker, body mass index (BMI) of 27.4 kg/m² (72 kg, 162 cm). She was also receiving cholecalciferol (25,000 IU every 2 weeks). At the time of transition to MRHC, she was on IRHC 7.5 mg AM + 5 mg midday + 2.5 mg PM (total 15 mg/day).

Tables 1 and 2 show the biochemical profiles before MRHR and after 4 months of therapy.

Table 1. Baseline biochemical profile (February 2024 – 8:00 AM, fasting, pre-dose on IRHC 7.5 mg + 5 mg + 2.5 mg)

ANALYTES (sn)	VALUES (sn)	ANALYTES (dx)	VALUES (dx)
Glucose	80 mg/dL (70–99 mg/dL)	HDL-C	93 mg/dL (50–90 mg/dL)
Insulin	6.5 µU/mL (4–25 µU/mL)	LDL-C	119 mg/dL (60–100 mg/dL)
HOMA-IR	1.25 (1.0–2.4)	17-OHP	56 ng/mL
HbA1c	35 mmol/mol (< 5.7%)	D4	6 ng/mL (0.4–3.4 ng/mL)
TG	51 mg/dL (<150 mg/dL)	DHEAS	150 µg/dL (99–340 µg/dL)
Na	141 mmol/L (135–145 mmol/L)	Testosterone	0.72 ng/mL (0.08–0.48 ng/mL)
K	4.33 mmol/L (3.5–5.0 mmol/L)	ACTH	183 pg/mL (7.2–52 pg/mL)
Renin	35.7 µIU/mL (4–46 µIU/mL)	Cortisol	84 ng/mL (53–185 ng/mL)
TC	222 mg/dL (125–200 mg/dL)		

Table 2. Post-MRHC biochemical profile after 4 months (July 2024 – 8:00 AM, fasting, pre-dose on MRHC 5+10 mg)

ANALYTES (sn)	VALUES (sn)	ANALYTES (dx)	VALUES (dx)
Glucose	84 mg/dL (70–99 mg/dL)	HDL-C	86 mg/dL (50–90 mg/dL)
Insulin	6 µU/mL (4–25 µU/mL)	LDL-C	110 mg/dL (60–100 mg/dL)
HOMA-IR	1.24 (1.0–2.4)	17-OHP	28.6 ng/mL
HbA1c	33 mmol/mol (< 5.7%)	D4	5.31 ng/mL (0.4–3.4 ng/mL)
TG	51 mg/dL (<150 mg/dL)	DHEAS	150 µg/dL (99–340 µg/dL)
Na	135.6 mmol/L (135–145 mmol/L)	Testosterone	0.63 ng/mL (0.08–0.48 ng/mL)
K	4.15 mmol/L (3.5–5.0 mmol/L)	ACTH	90.9 pg/mL (7.2–52 pg/mL)
Renin	29 µIU/mL (4–46 µIU/mL)	Cortisol	149 ng/mL (53–185 ng/mL)
TC	209 mg/dL (125–200 mg/dL)		

I. Biochemical and clinical response to MRHC therapy

Following the introduction of MRHC, the patient exhibited notable biochemical and subjective clinical improvements over four months. The most clinically relevant changes involved adrenal androgens and ACTH. 17-hydroxyprogesterone (17OHP) dropped from 56 to 28.6 ng/mL (–48.9%). Androstenedione decreased by 11.5%, and testosterone by 12.5%. ACTH levels halved (–50.3%), while cortisol dropped by 43.6%. The patient reported improved energy, restoration of regular menstrual cycles, and overall well-being. Metabolic markers showed modest changes: glucose levels rose slightly (+5%), insulin levels decreased (–

7.7%), and the Homeostasis Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) remained stable. Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) improved from 35 to 33 mmol/mol (−5.7%). The lipid profile showed modest changes: total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) decreased by 5.9%, 7.5%, and 7.6%, respectively, while triglycerides (TG) increased by 27.5% (still within normal limits).

The apparently unexpected reduction in HDL-C may be related to the overall lower exposure to exogenous cortisol during MRHC therapy (10 mg/day vs. 15 mg/day of IRHC), as exogenous cortisol is known to have a slight increase in HDL-C levels. These biochemical changes were paralleled by spontaneous conception four months into MRHC, despite previous suboptimal control on IRHC.

II. Pregnancy course and outcome

Upon confirmation of pregnancy in August 2024 (beta-human chorionic gonadotropin [*b*-HCG]: 2052 IU/L), MRHC was discontinued, and IRHC was reintroduced at the previous dose (7.5 mg morning, 5 mg midday, 2.5 mg evening). Partner genetic screening was negative, and genetic counseling confirmed that there was no increased risk of disease inheritance for the fetus.

Throughout the pregnancy, the patient remained clinically and biochemically stable. There was no need to increase the hydrocortisone dose at any trimester, as glycemia, electrolytes, and blood pressure remained within normal limits. Cortisol and ACTH levels followed expected physiological changes:

- 1° trimester: cortisol 66 ng/mL, ACTH 74.4 pg/mL
- 2° trimester: cortisol 70 ng/mL, ACTH 37.8 pg/mL
- 3° trimester: cortisol 104 ng/mL, ACTH 46.1 pg/mL.

Obstetric monitoring, including fetal growth and well-being assessments, remained normal throughout. Routine prenatal care proceeded without complications. The patient underwent standard fetal anomaly screening, including combined first-trimester screening and second-trimester anomaly scan, all of which were unremarkable. No signs of fetal adrenal hyperplasia or growth restriction were noted.

In April 2025, she delivered a healthy male infant via spontaneous vaginal delivery under appropriate peripartum stress-dose steroid coverage. The neonatal screening test for adrenal disorders was negative, and the newborn showed normal postnatal adaptation, with no evidence of adrenal insufficiency or virilization. According to the mother and pediatric evaluations, the infant remained healthy at follow-up.

Discussion

This case highlights the potential of MRHC to improve endocrine and reproductive outcomes in women with NCCAH. Spontaneous pregnancy occurred after just four months of MRHC therapy, despite years of suboptimal androgen control and menstrual irregularities on IRHC. NCCAH is associated with subfertility due to chronic hyperandrogenism, which can impair folliculogenesis and ovulation [5-7]. Suppression of adrenal androgens through glucocorticoid therapy remains the mainstay of management in women seeking pregnancy [8]. However, IRHC's short half-life often results in fluctuating cortisol exposure and ACTH-driven androgen production [2,8]. In contrast, MRHC mimics physiological cortisol secretion, with early-morning peaks that better suppress nocturnal ACTH surges, leading to more consistent androgen control [3]. In our case, this translated into a nearly 50% reduction in 17-hydroxyprogesterone and substantial declines in androstenedione, testosterone, and ACTH.

Although evidence supporting MRHC in the management of CAH is emerging, most studies to date have primarily focused on biochemical outcomes or long-term disease control, with a paucity of data on reproductive endpoints, limited to patients with the classic forms of CAH (CCAH). Nevertheless, evidence from clinical trials suggests the potential role of MRHC in restoring fertility, also in men (*Table 3*). In the phase 3 extension study comparing MRHC to standard GCs treatments (IRHC prednisone and prednisolone) in CCAH, MRHC resulted in menses restoration in eight patients, three spontaneous pregnancies and two partner pregnancies [4].

A post hoc analysis comparing MRHC to prednisolone, only one pregnancy was reported in a patient under MRHC [9]. These findings are supported by recent long-term follow-up data from patients treated with MRHC during phase 2 and 3 clinical trials, which reported a pregnancy rate of 13.5% in women and 13.8% of partner pregnancies in men. Of the five conceiving women, four had a normal course of pregnancy followed by live birth, while one had a spontaneous abortion [10]. Despite the lack of real-world data, this evidence suggests a potential benefit of MRHC for reproductive health.

To our knowledge, this is the first documented case of spontaneous conception after switching to MRHC in a patient with NCCAH, emphasizing its potential role in preconception care.

This case also raises the possibility that better ACTH suppression—not just total daily glucocorticoid dose may be key to restoring ovulatory function in NCCAH. While our patient received a lower total daily dose of cortisol on MRHC (15 mg IRHC vs. 10 mg MRHC), she achieved superior biochemical control and improved clinical outcomes. In fact, supraphysiologic glucocorticoid exposure is well known to impair the HPG axis [11]. By restoring a more physiological circadian cortisol rhythm, MRHC may simultaneously achieve more effective control of ACTH-driven androgen excess and minimize HPG axis suppression [12].

Importantly, MRHC was discontinued during pregnancy and replaced by IRHC, in line with current guidelines that recommend shorter-acting glucocorticoids during gestation due to limited data on MRHC safety in pregnancy [13,14]. Our patient maintained biochemical stability throughout pregnancy and delivered a healthy infant at term.

Limitations of this report include its single-patient nature and the lack of formal ovulatory monitoring with serial hormonal measurements (gonadotropins, progesterone, estradiol) or transvaginal ultrasounds. Nonetheless, the consistent hormonal improvements and temporal relationship with MRHC introduction support a causal link, highlighting its potential role in preconception care and fertility management of CCAH. Further studies are warranted to evaluate MRHC's role in the reproductive management of CAH, define optimal treatment duration before conception, and assess long-term maternal and fetal outcomes.

Conclusion

This case illustrates the therapeutic potential of MRHC in restoring fertility and achieving hormonal balance in women with NCCAH. The reduction in adrenal androgens and ACTH, along with improved subjective well-being and spontaneous ovulation, underscores the potential value of MRHC as a pre-conceptual tool.

While IRHC remains the standard during pregnancy, MRHC may represent a more physiological and effective alternative in women of reproductive age with subfertility. Further studies are needed to define its place in the reproductive management of CAH, evaluate predictive biochemical markers, and assess long-term maternal and fetal outcomes.

Statements

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Ethics Statement and Conflict of Interest Disclosures: Human subjects: Informed consent for treatment and open access publication was obtained or waived by all participants in this study for anonymized clinical data. The study followed the ethical guidelines established by the Declaration of Helsinki. **Animal subjects:** All authors have confirmed that this study did not involve animal subjects or tissue. **Conflicts of interest:** In compliance with [the ICMJE uniform disclosure form](#), all authors declare the following. **Payment/services info:** All authors have declared that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work. **Financial relationships:** All authors have declared that they have no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work. **Other relationships:** All authors have declared that there are no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

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Appendix

Table 3. Pregnancies and Partner Pregnancies Reported in CAH Patients Treated with MRHC

Study	Year	CAH Type	Total (F/M)	Mean Treatment Duration (months)	Mean MRHC Dose (mg/day)	Pregnancies (F)	Partner Pregnancies (M)	% Pregnancies (F)	% Partner Pregnancies (M)	Notes
Merke et al. [4] (phase 3 + extension MRHC vs standard GCs)	2021	Classical (CCAH)	122 (83 F / 39 M)	6 months (up to 18 months)	30 → 20 mg (median, tapering over 18 months)	3	2	3.6% (3/83)	5.1% (2/39)	Menses restored in 8 women (7 with MRHC, 1 with standard GCs)
Rees et al. [9] (RCT MRHC vs Prednisolone)	2024	Classical (CCAH)	48 (27 F / 21 M)	~6 months	5–20 mg (range, no tapering)	1	N.R.	3.7% (1/27)	N.R.	
Arlt et al. [10] (long-term follow-up)	2025	Classical (CCAH)	91 (62 F / 29 M)	median ~48 months	25 → 20 mg (tapering over 48 months)	5	4	8.1% (5/37)	13.8% (4/29)	% of pregnancies calculate out of fertile women < 50 years (n. 37)
Current case report	2025	Non-Classical (NCCAH)	1 female	4 months	10 mg MRHC vs 15 mg IRHC	1	N.A.	100% (1/1)	N.A.	First spontaneous pregnancy post-switch to MRHC in NCCAH.

Footnotes: Mean treatment duration and mean MRHC dose refer to the overall study population (not specified specifically for patients who achieved pregnancies)

Legend: F= females; M= males; CAH= congenital adrenal hyperplasia; CCAH= classic congenital adrenal hyperplasia; NCCAH= non classic congenital adrenal hyperplasia; GCs= glucocorticoids; MRHC= modified release hydrocortisone; mg= milligrams